

FORMATION OF MORAL RULES IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article discusses the tasks of moral education of preschool children and the views and opinions of Eastern thinkers in this area.*

Keywords: *morality, norm, personality, mental and physical maturity, spiritual maturity, behavior, meaning, social, attitude, behavior, laws and regulations, maturity, general, character, attitude, category.*

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ НРАВСТВЕННЫХ ПРАВИЛ У ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются задачи нравственного воспитания детей дошкольного возраста, взгляды и мнения мыслителей Востока в этой области.*

Ключевые слова: *мораль, норма, личность, умственная и физическая зрелость, духовная зрелость, поведение, смысл, социальное, отношение, поступок, законы и правила, зрелость, общее, характер, отношение, категория.*

It is known that without moral standards, it is difficult for a person to achieve spiritual and physical maturity and spiritual perfection. The word morality in Arabic means behavior, and it is a set of laws and rules that regulate social relations and personal behavior, and serves as a component of spirituality, a higher stage of personal perfection. The concept of morality has a general character and includes not individual relations, but relations in all spheres. This is called the moral category. The set of qualities that people combine in themselves, such as goodness, diligence, kindness, justice, honesty, humanity, patriotism, and collectivism, can be included in the principles of moral education. Examples of the qualities that moral consciousness combines in itself include good and evil, duty and conscience, and dignity. Elements of moral education are given in the family and in preschool educational organizations.

In the process of moral education, a child's moral qualities mature. In the process of developing moral qualities, first of all, they begin to consciously understand their relationships with others, and moral lessons develop in their relationships with peers and adults.

The results of psychological research show that the preschool age period is an important period in the spiritual, moral, and physical formation of a child. It is from this period that the moral qualities of a person begin to form under the influence of goal-oriented education. In addition, the preschool age of a child is such a meaningful and active period that it is the greatest stage in the psychological development of a child during this period, and the role of parents in helping their child become a mature person is very important. This period certainly leaves its mark on the child's future growth. Therefore, the preschool age period is extremely responsible in terms of its influence.

When a child reaches kindergarten age, serious changes occur in his psychological development. Because it is from this period that the child's independence expands. A preschool child has two powerful forces necessary for independent activity. First, he has a motor apparatus that is subordinated to him to a certain extent, and secondly, he has speech that allows him to interact with adults and peers quite freely.

That is why the behavior, moral qualities, actions, interests and needs of children of this age are sharply different from those of children of the first age. This, in turn, requires a different approach to the education of children of the first age and preschool children. During the preschool period, significant changes occur in their relationships with the environment. On the one hand, the child becomes much more free from the constant help of adults and moves away from them to some extent, and on the other hand, his relationships with adults begin to acquire a complex, multifaceted character. It is necessary to eliminate the mistakes made in the moral upbringing of children on their own. There are people in society who are rude, ignorant, unintelligent, drug addicts, who raise their hands against their parents and cause their children to live unhappy lives. This is due to the indifference of children to their upbringing.

In the moral education of preschool children, the upbringing of the child's mind, worldview, moral qualities, personal qualities and behavior is an important factor in his development. The following tasks have been identified in the moral education of preschool children:

- 1) to educate children's moral feelings and behavior;
- 2) to cultivate moral culture and positive emotions;
- 3) to develop moral behavior skills.

The moral education of preschool children is carried out based on clear criteria.

If a fully developed person has the best qualities of humanity: love, compassion, justice and piety, modesty, faith and beliefs, then such qualities are the opposite in the upbringing of immoral, worthless people. The reputation of each nation and people is determined by the behavior, morality, etiquette, good and bad qualities and virtues of people. The norms of moral education serve as the basis for the legal norms of each nation. People who have acquired moral knowledge, can control themselves in any situation, and behave in accordance with moral norms are considered spiritually mature, morally educated people. All this is instilled in the minds of children in the preschool educational organization and family. In the moral education of preschool children, the hadith, fairy tales, stories, parables, proverbs, and narrations that reflect the conflict between good and evil are used as a basis for example.

Eastern thinkers paid special attention to the upbringing of the family and children. Abu Rayhan Beruni connects the moral qualities and moral concepts of a person with the nature of a person. And human nature is formed in the family. This indicates that the influence and example of parents in raising a child are extremely great. Beruni pays attention to the purity of the body and soul. If cleanliness, purity, and order are established in the family, spiritual purity is formed here. This idea encourages not only to keep the body clean, but also to work hard. This encourages work. His idea about the soul and movement is closely related to the idea of the unity of the human body and the purity of the soul. In our opinion, the connection between physical health and spiritual and moral knowledge in the upbringing of preschool children develops in accordance with today's requirements. The main goal of moral education for preschool children is to raise young people to be happy, respected, and selfless people of their time.

In conclusion, it can be said that the complexity of upbringing is that it never ends, that is, it is a continuous process that lasts from the birth of a child until the end of his life. In addition, children who have been raised in place of one generation need to be raised again. This shows the relentless cyclicity and eternity of upbringing.

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